

Improve the Efficiency of Social Relationship Management of Students at Current Medical Training Facilities

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Abstract:- General student management, social relationships of students at medical training institutions in particular yes location, special role making an important contribution to training quality human resources - a decisive factor for rapid and sustainable socio-economic development; have a direct impact on the results of education and training of the school and the society. In the face of increasing growth in goals, requirements for training medical students and the educational and training mission of medical training institutions in the current period, posing a requirement to improve the efficiency of students' social relationship management at the university. current medical training institutions.

Management of the social relationships of students at medical institutions is the sum total of the planned, purported effects of management entities in medical institutions on students through through defined relationships in order to orient, control and develop their good social relations, contribute to educating and developing the personality of medical students to meet the goals, training needs of medical staff, future doctor for society.

Keyword:- Social Relations, Medical Students, Medical Training Institutions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Be well aware of the position, role and necessity of the jobmanaging social relationships of medical students, over the years, committees, managers and commanders at all levels in medical training institutions have always paid attention to leadership and direction for the management of medical students. the social relationships of students in general and medical students in particular. Therefore, the social relationships of medical students are basically strictly managed, shaping, strengthening and developing positive relationships; promptly solve, overcome and prevent the arising of negative relationships in the life of medical students. Contributing to building a team of medical staff, doctors basically meeting the requirements of qualifications, qualifications and capacity in performing tasks after graduation.

However, due to many objective and subjective reasons, the management of students' social relationships at medical training institutions still has limitations: The leadership and direction of some levels committees, managers, and commanders at all levels in managing the social relationships of medical students are not regular and proper; content management of social relationships of medical students is not comprehensive; Forms and methods of managing social relationships of medical students have not been regularly innovated and applied flexibly in association with the conditions and characteristics of each unit and medical students in different institutions. training department; The results of managing some social relationships of students at some medical training institutions are still limited. These limitations are due to many objective and subjective reasons, of which the main reason is subjective.

II. CONTENT OF RESEARCHING

Currently, in the face of the rapid changes of the world, the region, the country, the task situation of the health sector, the management of social relationships of students at the training institutions. Medicine is affected both positively and negatively by a number of factors. Therefore, in order to improve the efficiency of the management of social relationships of students at medical training institutions is conducted strictly and scientifically, requiring the subjects and forces to thoroughly grasp and Here are a few basic solutions:

➤ *Firstly, raising awareness and promoting the responsibility of the subjects and forces involved in managing social relationships of medical students.*

This is an important solution, contributing to the orientation of the process of managing the social relationships of students at medical training institutions. Because, right perception will be the basis for right action; Right awareness will create inner motivation, orientation, directing activities and promote positivity, initiative, creativity, overcome all difficulties to achieve the defined purpose.

Practice shows, Only when the actors and forces are properly and sufficiently aware of the management of social relationships can they ensure the management of their social

relationships. students at medical training institutions carried out efficiently and with the specified quality.

Toraising awareness and promoting responsibility for the forces involved in managing the social relationships of students at current medical training institutions need do well the education, propaganda and awareness raising for the forces, especially the leaders, managers and commanders at all levels about the position, role, urgency to manage the relationships well. the social system of students at current medical training institutions. In addition, it is necessary to make the subjects and forces see the current status of the quality of social relationship management, the advantages, difficulties and challenges in improving the efficiency of social relationship management. of students at current medical training institutions so as to have appropriate and effective management measures and forms. Party committees, managers and commanders at all levels at medical training institutions need to do well in assigning specific tasks to each force so that they are properly and sufficiently aware and uphold their responsibilities in the course of implementation. perform management duties. To step by step consolidate and standardize the contingent of cadres and lecturers in sufficient quantity, ensuring good quality, especially the staff in charge of managing medical students.

For party organizations at all levels, directly party organizations in student management units at medical training institutions, it is necessary to have thematic leadership content and measures on management of social relationships. of students. In particular, it is necessary to attach importance to leaders to promote the synergy of organizations and individuals inside and outside the unit to effectively manage students' social relationships. Link management of students' social relationships with building strong organizations within the unit.

For agencies and faculty, it is necessary to regularly monitor, coordinate and guide student management units to effectively carry out political and ideological education. Strengthening good coordination with the Party committees and commanders of student management units in building a healthy pedagogical and cultural environment, organizing useful, practical and psychologically appropriate playgrounds, Youth interests attract a large number of students to participate. Medical student management units need to thoroughly grasp the issued directives, guidelines and regulations; at the same time, actively and proactively, research, master and implement seriously and scientifically, suitable to management conditions, circumstances and subjects.

➤ *Secondly, regularly study, supplement and perfect regulations and regulations and strictly maintain all regimes and habits in the management of social relationships of students at medical training institutions currently*

This is an important solution, creating a legal basis and guidance for the management of students' social relationships at current medical training institutions. This is also an objective

requirement of the management of education and training in general and the management of social relationships of medical students in particular to suit the current situation. The implementation of this solution contributes to the development and improvement of regulations and regulations along with strictly maintaining all rules and regulations of medical training institutions. Ensure strict management of students' social relationships at medical training institutions.

The maintenance of strict implementation of regulations and regulations on management of social relationships of students at medical training institutions must be carried out regularly in connection with the implementation, strictly maintain all regimes and rules 's activities medical training institutions. To make this solution well done, Party committees, managers, functional agencies at all levels need to review the current regulations, adjust, supplement and complete the contents that are no longer appropriate to suit the development of the situation, avoid the situation of conservatism, stagnation, fear of change, causing conflicts in awareness and actions of staff, lecturers and students. To ensure the coverage and adjustment of the social relationships of medical students with other forces inside and outside the medical training institution, without infringing upon the legitimate rights, legitimate rights and democratic rights of medical students. each student.

Continue to strengthen leadership in strictly maintaining the regimes, regulations and routines of the training institution in association with building a pedagogical cultural environment, a democratic, healthy, open and sincere atmosphere among the students. students with other subjects and forces. Well perform the work of legal education, political and ideological education, education of the sense of organization and discipline; regularly train and foster communication skills, life skills and bravery for medical students. Managers at all levels and the teaching staff must be exemplary in compliance with their subordinates, in front of students, must be standard in compliance with the regimes, regulations and routines of the training institution, worthy of being an example to subordinates, students learn and follow. In addition, it is necessary to promptly capture and handle the manifestations and violations of students at medical training institutions in solving social relationships. On the basis of current regulations and the extent of the incident, to give appropriate forms and measures to both ensure legality and demonstrate the humanity of the medical training institution. Always take education, construction and encouragement to make progress of the wrongdoers as the main thing. Do not absolutize the administrative handling, nor relax or take lightly for cases with repeated violations.

➤ *Third, actively innovate the content and form of management of students' social relationships at current medical training institutions.*

This is the solution with the most important position and role, the most frequent, continuous and direct impact on the quality and effectiveness of managing students' social relationships at current medical training institutions. now. Renovation of contents, forms and management measures is the

process of researching, selectively inheriting, supplementing, improving and applying existing contents, forms and measures in order to improve quality and effectiveness. performance management of social relationships of students at current medical training institutions.

Renovate the content, form, and measures to manage social relationships of students at medical training institutions must be derived from the characteristics of the process of formation and development of relationships and psychological characteristics, individual personality, field of activity, responsibilities, tasks and operating environment of each individual. students at medical training institutions. Must firmly grasp the bases to determine the appropriate content and form of managing students' social relationships. Along with that, regularly renew the content of grasping, reporting, reflecting the ideological situation and social relationships of students. Actively research, master and thoroughly implement regulations and guidelines on management of social relationships of students at medical training institutions. At the same time, it is necessary to diversify and renew forms of management of students' social relationships. Regularly monitor, check and supervise the social relationships of students with extremely difficult circumstances in their families or in study, work and daily activities to promptly report, reflect and handle. In the process of managing students' social relationships, when detecting signs of violations of discipline, regulations, violations of moral quality, lifestyle, unhealthy relationships, it is necessary to investigate. carefully, carefully, have objective, accurate and timely conclusions. At the same time, it is necessary to maintain, grow and further promote the good relationship with the Party committee, government, local people in the area, sister unit and resident student's family for effective management. students' social relationships.

➤ *Fourth, promote the positivity, initiative and self-discipline in self-management of social relationships of students at current medical training institutions.*

This is one of the solutions basic, important, meaningful key in improving the quality of management activities of social relationships of students at medical training institutions Currently. At the same time, it is an important basis to turn the management process into the self-management process of students; help students realize the right role, master themselves to raise themselves up to the level of the goal, training requirements and mission requirements in the future working position.

To promote activeness, initiative, self-discipline in self-management of social relationships of students at medical training institutions now need enhance education, raise awareness, promote students' responsibility for management and self-management of their social relationships. Accordingly, organizations and student management forces must uphold their roles and responsibilities in education, raise awareness, maintain strict and regular management activities; creating a favourable environment and conditions for students to promote their initiative, creativity, and self-discipline to comply with

management, turning the management process into self-management and self-mastery in all circumstances.

Regularly pay attention to and create favorable conditions for students in all aspects to self-discipline and self-manage social relationships. Having an appropriate mechanism in management; create a favorable environment for students to follow the regimes and regulations of the training institution, participate in building and maintaining a healthy pedagogical cultural environment, and implement a grassroots democratic and cultural institution; guide students to be able to detect, distinguish and choose positive social relationships and avoid negative social relationships that are contrary to the regulations of the training institution. Motivating and guiding students to actively, actively practice and self-manage; must set requirements that require each student to have effort and high will in learning and training.

III. SOLUTION

Improving the efficiency of the management of social relationships of students at medical training institutions is now an issue of both importance, urgency, fundamental and long-term significance, of theoretical and practical significance. deeply. Facing the development and requirements of the current situation, subjects and forces need to promote synchronous implementation and creative application of solutions to improve the efficiency of students' management of social relationships at the university. medical training institutions. Thereby, making an important contribution to the successful implementation of the central political task of the training institutions and improving the quality of medical staff in the current period.

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